

Variables that may influence entrepreneurial intention among university students : a review of the literature

Les variables qui peuvent influencer l'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants universitaires : une revue de la littérature

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to present a review of the literature on variables that may influence students' entrepreneurial intention, as well as the theories that underlying our research work. Several theories have been used to explain entrepreneurial intention, including the theory of entrepreneurial event of Sokol and Shapero and Ajzen's theory of planned behavior. But among students in particular, it is necessary to ask what factors spark the idea of starting a business. After reading several articles in the literature on entrepreneurial intention, we were able to identify three essential variables that affect entrepreneurial intention : the desire to undertake, the social factor, i.e., the environment and the entourage, and the entrepreneurial capacity, which is manifested in financial and informational resources. Thus, the results of our study, based on 26 articles that deal with the determinants of entrepreneurial intention, were generated using the Nvivo software.

Keywords : entrepreneurial intention ; Ajzen's theory ; entrepreneurial desire ; social factors ; entrepreneurial capacity.

Résumé

L'objectif de cet article est de présenter une revue de la littérature sur les variables qui peuvent influencer l'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants, ainsi que les théories qui soutiennent notre travail de recherche. Plusieurs théories ont été utilisées pour expliquer l'intention entrepreneuriale, notamment la théorie de l'événement entrepreneurial de Sokol et Shapero et la théorie du comportement planifié d'Ajzen. Mais chez les étudiants en particulier, il est nécessaire de s'interroger sur les facteurs qui peuvent déclencher l'idée de créer une entreprise. Après avoir lu plusieurs articles de la littérature sur l'intention entrepreneuriale, nous avons pu identifier trois variables essentielles qui agissent sur l'intention entrepreneuriale notamment, le désir d'entreprendre, le facteur social c'est-à-dire l'environnement et l'entourage et la capacité d'entreprendre qui se manifeste dans les ressources financières et informationnelles. Ainsi, les résultats de notre étude, basée sur 26 articles qui traitent les déterminants de l'intention entrepreneuriale, ont été générés via le logiciel Nvivo.

Mots clés : intention entrepreneuriale ; théorie d'Ajzen ; désir d'entreprendre ; facteurs sociaux ; capacité d'entreprendre.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is a strategic lever for the development of society through the creation of wealth, jobs and the fight against unemployment. Today, Morocco encourages the use of entrepreneurship to alleviate the problems of insufficient employment. This is the reason why Morocco has adopted policies to accompany and support business foundations. Certainly entrepreneurship is not a new concept, but it dates back several years (1930). In his article on "The field of entrepreneurship: history, evolution and trends", (Filion, 1997) presents two categories of thinkers: economists and behaviourists. The latter are composed of psychologists, psychoanalysts and sociologists. They are very interested in the behavior of the entrepreneur to understand entrepreneurship. According to behaviourists, it is necessary to study in depth the behaviour and the characteristics of the entrepreneur, in particular the psychological and social factors which can lead the individual to launch out in the entrepreneurship. For (Ajzen, 1991), who is a social psychologist, he explains the behavior of the entrepreneur by three constructs, namely attitudes, social norms, and perceived behavioral control. (Shapero & Sokol, 1982), for their part, suggest the theory of the entrepreneurial event by referring to four factors, namely negative displacement, positive displacement, the degree of desirability, and the degree of feasibility. Based on these different theories, researchers hypothesize about entrepreneurial intention, and suggest variables that explain the behavior of the potential entrepreneur (Benredjem & Sahut, 2016; Boissin, Branchet, et al., 2009; Koubaa et Eddine, 2012; Przepiorka, 2017; Tounés, 2006). From these mobilized theories we can therefore ask the following question: what are the explanatory factors that determine the entrepreneurial intention of university students?

To try to find answers to this question, we went through several steps that allowed us to select 26 articles that deal with the subject of entrepreneurial intention, particularly among students. We then drew up a table that clarifies all the variables used by researchers to predict entrepreneurial intentions, and finally we inserted our data into the Nvivo software, which allowed us to obtain results on the frequencies of the words used. To conduct this research we first propose a literature review on the key concepts and theories used. Then, we highlight the research methodology on which our work is based. Then, we analyze the different articles selected by drawing up a table. Finally, we conclude with the presentation of the results of our analysis, and we present the discussions of our research.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Entrepreneurial intent

The notion of entrepreneurial intention has attracted the interest of several researchers since the 1980s. In 1990, the term "intention" was replaced by the term "strategic intention", which means, according to (Varraut, 1998), a set of tasks characterized by a mental attitude that leads the intention of the owner and manager of the company to the research and development of methods and specific tools, whose objective is to achieve a specific strategic project. This definition has been developed over time by several researchers, including (Thompson, 2009) who defines entrepreneurial intention as a belief evidenced by the individual that stipulates the creation of a business in the future. According to (Benredjem & Sahut, 2016), intention is a mental manifestation that involves a willingness, a conviction to achieve a certain goal such as the creation of a business. In social psychology, entrepreneurial intention is therefore a degree of determination and motivational factors that the individual holds to achieve something. This definition has been taken up by several researchers, adding that intention is a cognitive structure of both a goal and the tools to achieve it, its identification implies an early identification of the goal, and is determined by self-efficacy which is conditioned by awareness and entrepreneurial guidance (Galloway & Brown, 2002; Krueger & Carsrud, 1993; Tounés, 2006). Intention is also influenced by contextual variables and is part of a process composed of four stages, namely propensity, intention, decision and action (Tounés, 2006). In a university setting, entrepreneurial intent is associated with coursework, including entrepreneurial training (Bacq et al., 2017; Hahn et al., 2020). (Sarasvathy, 2014), believes that it is very important to first know the traits, abilities and attributes of each individual, then to strengthen the entrepreneurial knowledge, and to act on the social network of the potential entrepreneur if we want to stimulate the entrepreneurial intention. For our purposes, we consider that the intention is a phase of the entrepreneurial creation process, which is positioned before the act of undertaking. It is conditioned by a certain number of environmental, social, cultural and economic factors.

1.2 Theories mobilized

The theory of the entrepreneurial event of Sokol and Shapero, and the theory of planned behavior have found their interest in several fields of research, notably in entrepreneurship. Hence, their abundant use in research on entrepreneurial intention (Bell, 2018; Benredjem and Sahut, 2016; Boissin, Branchet, et al., 2009; Doğan, 2015; Koubaa and Eddine, 2012;

Laguía et al., 2017; Li and Wu, 2019; Przepiorka, 2017; Tomy & Pardede, 2020; Vélez et al., 2020).

Therefore, we believe it is necessary to explain the two theories that are so often used by researchers to study entrepreneurial intention in order to better identify the explanatory variables of entrepreneurial intention.

1.2.1 The theory of the entrepreneurial event of Shapero and Sokol (1982)

(Shapero & Sokol, 1982) are the initiators of the intentions approach in the field of entrepreneurship and their model has been taken up and verified by (Krueger & Carsrud, 1993). (Shapero & Sokol, 1982) present the social dimensions of entrepreneurship and pose a model (**Fig 1**) that describes the formation of the entrepreneurial event. They suggest that the formation of the entrepreneurial event is the result of the interaction between situational and cultural factors and postulate that for a person to begin a transformation in his or her life, an action must result in such a decision. They therefore refer to four essential factors that explain the entrepreneurial intention, namely: 1- Negative displacements (redundancy, dissatisfaction at work) 2- Positive displacements that concern (obtaining a gain or an inheritance) 3- Factors of perceived desirability (culture, colleagues, family) 4- Feasibility (financing, advice, help, training).

Fig 1. The model of the formation on the entrepreneurial event of Sokol and Shapero, 1982

Source : Sokol and Shapero, 1982

1.2.2 The theory of planned behavior of Ajzen (1991)

For many researchers, psychology is a means of predicting the behavior of each individual, which is why some researchers have mobilized, in entrepreneurship, the theory of planned behavior presented by (Ajzen, 1991) which explains the behavior of the individual by three constructs, namely attitudes, subjective norms and behavioral control (**Fig 2**). Attitudes associated with behavior lead to social and cultural factors that influence the values of the individual. In the field of entrepreneurship, the more interest there is in innovation and risk-taking, the more businesses are created. Defeat in entrepreneurial ventures and previous experiences also influence the individual and therefore their desire to create. This is explained as desirability by Sokol and Shapero. Subjective norms are the result of social pressure, wishes from friends and family regarding becoming an entrepreneur. They refer to desirability in Sokol and Shapero's model. Finally, perceptions of behavioral control refer to the knowledge, skills, and financial resources that the individual has to carry out the intention. This is called feasibility in Sokol and Shapero's model.

Fig 2. La théorie du comportement planifié (Ajzen 1991)

Source: Ajzen, 1991

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection method

In a first step, we typed the word "entrepreneurial intention", and this gave us 13,000 results. In a second step, we typed in the keyword "entrepreneurial intention of students" in order to better define our results, and so that they are related to our research topic. We then obtained 6880 results.

In a third step we excluded searches based on the title of the article, which reduced the number of results to 2810. In a 4th and 5th step we tried to narrow down our search further and we sorted on the basis of the abstract, or on the basis of the full text concerning abstracts that were more or less ambiguous. Thus, we obtained 460 results.

Finally, we excluded repeated searches, and those containing unclear data. Thus, we obtained 60 results. It should be noted that we excluded all research that did not mobilize Ajzen's or Sokol and Shapero's theory. We then retained 26 articles dealing with the determinants of entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, we summarize our methodology in the following steps (Table 1).

Table 1. Excluded and retained items

Step number	Steps of the census	Number of excluded items	Number of articles retained
<i>Step 1:</i> <u>13 000</u>	<i>Step 2 :</i> <i>entrepreneurial intention of students</i>	6120	6880
	<i>Step 3:</i> Title	4070	2810
	<i>Step 4:</i> Abstract	1400	1410
	<i>Step 5:</i> Full text	950	460
<i>Step 6</i> <u>460</u>	<i>Step 7:</i> research identified	200	260
	<i>Step 8:</i> thesis/communication work	200	60
	<i>Step 9:</i> research mobilizing Ajzen's theory	35	25
Number of articles selected			26

Source : Ourselves

3. ANALYSIS OF COLLECTED DATA

The presentation of the collected data is made in the form of a table with 5 entries (Table2) :

- 1st entry: title
- 2nd entry: author
- 3rd entry: country
- 4th entry : issue

- 5th entry: variables

Because of the variability of the terminology used by each researcher, we have tried to group the variables according to the category to which they belong. For example:

- "environment", "surroundings", "friends", "family" are grouped into: social norms.
- "Abilities", "training", "experiences" are grouped into: behavioral control.
- "Motivations", "failure", "gain", "resignation" into: attitudes

Table 2. variables mobilized by the researchers

Title	Author	Country	Issue	Variables
Volume 6 : Numéro 2 Prediction en employment status choice intentions	(Kolvereid, 1996)	Norway	What are the elements that influence the entrepreneurial intention ?	Attitudes, social norms, perceived behavioral control
Entrepreneurial intent among students : intent model in Asia, Scandinavia and the USA	(Autio et al., 1997)	Asia Scandinavian USA	What are the factors influencing the development of entrepreneurial intention?	The image of entrepreneurship, attitudes, the university
Entrepreneurship as a potential career: an assessment in a university setting	(Filion, 2002)	Canada	What are students' perceptions of entrepreneurship?	Student perceptions
A longitudinal study of the entrepreneurial intentions of university students	(Audet, 2004)	Canada	What impact do desirability and feasibility have on the formation of entrepreneurial intention?	Desirability (attitudes, subjective norms), feasibility (perceived behavioral control)
L'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants : le cas français	(Tounés, 2006)	France	Can entrepreneurship training in academic institutions influence the entrepreneurial intentions of French students?	attitudes, subjective norms, perceptions of behavioral control
Students' beliefs about starting a business	(Boissin et al., 2007)	France	How do students value an entrepreneurial career? What is the difference between those who have received entrepreneurial training and other students?	Attitudes, social norms, feasibility (behavioral control)
Entrepreneurial intentions of university students: a comparison between France, Tunisia and Canada	(Gasse et al., 2007)	France Tunisia Canada	How can students' values, attitudes, and behaviors initiate them to create a business, their own work, or intend to have their own project?	Desirability (social norms), feasibility (behavioral control), beliefs about entrepreneurship, personality traits (attitudes and motivations)
Determinants of students' intention to start a business	(Boissin, Chollet, et al., 2009)	France - Arab countries	What are students' beliefs and attitudes towards entrepreneurship?	Attitudes, social norms, perceived behavioral control
Comparison of students' entrepreneurial intentions: France - Arab countries	(Boissin, Branchet, et al., 2009)	France - Arab countries	What are the elements acting on students' entrepreneurial intention?	Behavioral beliefs, normative beliefs, control beliefs

Table 2. continued

Title	Author	Country	Issue	Variables
The entrepreneurial intention of young graduates	(Boudabbous , 2011)	Tunisia	What factors make young graduates want to start a business?	Attitudes, subjective or social norms, behavioral control
Entrepreneurial intention of students in Morocco: a PLS analysis	(Koubaa & Eddine 2012)	Morocco	What are the factors that can influence entrepreneurial intention among students in Morocco?	attitudes, desirability, feasibility
The effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of university students in Turkey	(Doğan, 2015)	Turkey	What are the factors that influence the entrepreneurial intention of university students a few months before starting their professional career in Turkey?	Behavioral control (training), social norms (entrepreneurial parents), desirability.
Crossed perspectives on the determinants of students' entrepreneurial intention	(Benredjem & Sahut, 2016)	Algeria	In a distinct environment, what are the determinants that explain entrepreneurial intention among students?	attitudes, perceived behavioral control, subjective norms
Psychological determinants of entrepreneurial success and life satisfaction	(Przepiorka, 2017)	Poland	Why do some entrepreneurs succeed in the pre-launch phase, while others do not? And to what extent can the psychological character be a determining factor in the success of an entrepreneurial project?	Action orientations related to decision, action orientations related to failures (failure), hope, will.
Academic entrepreneurship in Spanish universities: An analysis of the determinants of entrepreneurial intention	(Miranda et al., 2017)	Spain	What are the determinants of entrepreneurial intention?	Subjective norms, Attitudes, Behavioral control
Effect of entrepreneurship education programs on the entrepreneurial intention of university students.	(González López et al., 2017)	Spain	What is the impact of entrepreneurship training on students' entrepreneurial intention?	Attitudes, Self-efficacy, Social norms, Entrepreneurship training

Table 2. continued

Title	Author	Country	Issue	Variables
Validation of the Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire in a sample of university students in Colombia.	(Laguía et al., 2017)	Colombia	What are the psychosocial factors that may lead the student to entrepreneurship?	Subjective norms, attitudes, behavioral control
Impact of subjective social norm on sustainable entrepreneurship intention: a case study.	(Gálvez-Albarracín et al., 2018)	Colombia	What is the level of interest among Valle University students in starting a business?	Subjective norms, attitudes, behavioral control
Entrepreneurial education and students entrepreneurial intention: does team cooperation matter?	(Li & Wu, 2019)	China	What impact does entrepreneurship training have on students' entrepreneurial intention?	self-efficacy, entrepreneurial passion, team cooperation, entrepreneurship training
Determinants of entrepreneurial intention among Dosso students	H. Moctar (2020)	Niger	What are the determining factors in the process of triggering the entrepreneurial intention of students: the University of Dosso in Niger?	Attitude, subjective norms, behavioral control
Entrepreneurship education as a predictor of entrepreneurial intention of university students.	(Vélez et al., 2020)	Ecuador (South America)	What is the impact of entrepreneurship training on university students?	Attitude, subjective norms, behavioral control
Entrepreneurship intention in Mexico City students.	(García & Adame, 2020)	Mexico	What aspects influence the entrepreneurial intention of students in Mexico?	Attitude, subjective norms, behavioral control
Structural equation modeling to determine students' entrepreneurial intentions	(Idrovo Poveda et al., 2020)	Ecuador (South America)	What are the key indicators that can help generate entrepreneurial behavior among students ?	Attitude, subjective norms, behavioral control
The entrepreneurial intention of students to the test of gender stereotypes: case of the University of Bejaia	(ADJOUT & BOUMOUL A, 2020)	Algeria	What is the role of socially constructed gender stereotypes in entrepreneurial intentions?	Attitude, subjective norms, behavioral control

Source : ourselves

Fig 4. Summary of the variables mentioned

Source : ourselves

5. DISCUSSION

In light of this analysis, we note that the variables: attitudes, social norms and perceived control are the most recurrent in several research studies dealing with the issue, and that their degree of relevance is relative and varies from one context to another. It is obvious that the variables found will have an impact, whether positive or negative, on the intention to start a business, but in our opinion, we believe that the perceived control variable, which relates to financing and entrepreneurial training, is the most important factor for starting a business. In Morocco, for example, several programs have been set up to support potential entrepreneurs, such as "Crédit Jeunes promoteurs", "Moukawalati", "Injaz". But it appears that the budget allocated to young entrepreneurs is insufficient, which hinders their ambitions. Especially since financial institutions seek their interest and act in terms of gain and risk. They do not want to take the risk of non-payment in case of decline of the company. It should also be noted that the majority of students from disadvantaged backgrounds (Ammari, 2022) are not interested in entrepreneurship, as their main concern after graduation is to seek employment in the public sector to escape poverty.

Conclusion

To conclude, it is important to remember that this research work has allowed us to identify the variables that explain entrepreneurial intention through different behavioral theories. Indeed, for Ajzen (1991), the behavior of the individual can be explained by three constructs:

- Attitudes: which involve the degree of evaluation, attraction or aspiration, favorable or unfavorable, that the individual has of a well-determined behavior. Attitudes can be synonymous with intrinsic and extrinsic motivations;
- Social norms: the result of social pressure on the individual's future, notably from family, friends, employers, or faculty;
- Perceived behavioral control: which incorporates the availability of resources, opportunities, disincentives, skills, academic training, or work experience.

It is therefore appropriate to state that the three variables in Ajzen's model have all been applied in research that concerns students' entrepreneurial intentions. However, their impact on intentions varies from one context and sample to another.

This research study contributes to the updating of previous studies, to find other variables that can influence the entrepreneurial act and to evolve the thinking on the subject. Without forgetting also that this work could serve as a starting point for a researcher to test the variables and verify the impact of each of them on the entrepreneurial intention.

However, given that it is very difficult to assert that anyone who has an intention will act in an entrepreneurial manner. It is therefore necessary to reflect on other variables that can influence intention and consequently the act of entrepreneurship. The contribution of the theories presented in this article to the field of entrepreneurship is undeniable, but it is clear that they cannot be generalized to all social categories. Thus, we propose to reflect on other variables that aim to better define the problem of entrepreneurship, and to question the effectiveness of university education in promoting entrepreneurship by asking the following questions:

1. What skills are required to teach entrepreneurship?
2. How should it be taught?
3. Wouldn't it be advisable to extend entrepreneurship education to high schools in order to foster an entrepreneurial culture and spirit among high school students, and therefore better motivate them to become entrepreneurs later on.

References

- Adjout, S., et Boumoula, S. (2020). L'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants à l'épreuve des stéréotypes de genre. Cas de l'université de Bejaia. *The Algerian Journal of Economic Development* 320-305
- AMMARIS. (2022) «Analysis of the determinants of entrepreneurship of young rural in Morocco», *Revue Internationale des Sciences de Gestion* «Volume 5: Numéro 4» pp: 25-33
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- Audet, J. (2004). A longitudinal study of the entrepreneurial intentions of university students. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 10(1), 3-16.
- Autio, E., Keeley, R. H., Klofsten, M., & Ulfstedt, T. (1997). Entrepreneurial intent among students : Testing an intent model in Asia, Scandinavia and USA.
- Bacq, S., Ofstein, L. F., Kickul, J. R., & Gundry, L. K. (2017). Perceived entrepreneurial munificence and entrepreneurial intentions : A social cognitive perspective. *International Small Business Journal*, 35(5), 639-659.
- Barbosa, S. D., de Oliveira, W. M., Fayolle, A., & Barbosa, F. V. (s. d.). Perceptions culturelles et intention d'entreprendre des étudiants : Une comparaison France-Brésil.
- Bell, R. (2018). The impact and support of constructivist learning environments to develop entrepreneurial and enterprising graduates to enhance employability [PhD Thesis]. University of Huddersfield.
- Benredjem, R., & Sahut, J.-M. (2016). Regards croisés sur les déterminants de l'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants. *Gestion* 2000, 33(5), 113-148.
- Boissin, J.-P., Chollet, B., & Emin, S. (2007). Les croyances des étudiants envers la création d'entreprise. *Revue française de gestion*, 11, 25-43.
- Boissin, J.-P., Branchet, B., Emin, S., & Herbert, J. I. (2009). Students and entrepreneurship : A comparative study of France and the United States. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 22(2), 101-122.
- Boudabbous, S. (2011). L'intention entrepreneuriale des jeunes diplômés. *Revue libanaise de gestion et d'économie*, 4(6), 1-20.

- Doğan, E. (2015). The effect of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of university students in Turkey. *Ekonometri ve istatistik e-Dergisi*, 23, 79-93.
- Filion, L. J. (1997). Le champ de l'entrepreneuriat : Historique, évolution, tendances. *Revue internationale PME Économie et gestion de la petite et moyenne entreprise*, 10(2), 129-172.
- Filion, L. J. (2002). L'entrepreneuriat comme carrière potentielle Une évaluation en milieu universitaire Louis Jacques Filion, Danielle L'Heureux, Christophe Kadji-Youaleu, François Bellavance École des HEC de Montréal. *Cahier de recherche*2002.
- Galloway, L., & Brown, W. (2002). Entrepreneurship education at university : A driver in the creation of high growth firms? *Education and training*.
- Gasse, Y., Camion, C., & Ghamgui, A. (2007). Les intentions entrepreneuriales des étudiants universitaires : Une comparaison France-Tunisie-Canada. *Faculté des sciences de l'administration, Université Laval*.
- García, M. L. S., & Adame, M. E. C. (2020). Intención de emprendimiento en los estudiantes de la Ciudad de México. *RAN-Revista Academia & Negocios*, 5(2)
- Gálvez-Albarracín, E. J., Guauña-Aguilar, R. A., & Pérez-Urbe, R. I. (2018). Impacto de la norma social subjetiva en la intención de emprendimiento sostenible : Un caso de estudio con estudiantes colombianos. *Revista Escuela de Administración de Negocios*, 85, 57-74
- González López, M. J., Perez-Lopez, M. C., & Rodriguez Ariza, L. R. (2017). Efecto de los programas de educación en emprendimiento sobre la intención Emprendedora de los estudiantes universitarios. *Economía industrial*, 404.
- Hahn, D., Minola, T., Bosio, G., & Cassia, L. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurship education on university students' entrepreneurial skills : A family embeddedness perspective. *Small Business Economics*, 55(1), 257-282.
- Idrovo Poveda, F. K., Verdesoto Velástegui, O. S., Valencia Núñez, E. R., & Córdova, V. H. (2020). Modelo de ecuaciones estructurales para determinar la intención de emprendimiento de estudiantes de posgrado. *Revista de Metodos Cuantitativos para la Economía y la Empresa*, 30. *European research on management and business economics*, 23(2), 113-122.
- Kolvereid, L. (1996). Prediction of employment status choice intentions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and practice*, 21(1), 47-58.

- Koubaa, S., & Eddine, A. S. (2012). L'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants au Maroc : Une analyse PLS de la méthode des équations structurelles. Actes du 11ème.
- Krueger, N. F., & Carsrud, A. L. (1993). Entrepreneurial intentions : Applying the theory of planned behaviour. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 5(4), 315-330.
- Laguía, A., Moriano, J. A., Gámez, J. A., & Molero, F. (2017). Validación del Cuestionario de Intención Emprendedora en una muestra de estudiantes universitarios de Colombia. *Universitas Psychologica*, 16(1).
- Li, L., & Wu, D. (2019). Entrepreneurial education and students' entrepreneurial intention : Does team cooperation matter? *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 9(1), 1-13.
- Miranda, F. J., Chamorro-Mera, A., & Rubio, S. (2017). Academic entrepreneurship in Spanish universities : An analysis of the determinants of entrepreneurial intention.
- Przepiorka, A. M. (2017). Psychological determinants of entrepreneurial success and life-satisfaction. *Current Psychology*, 36(2), 304-315.
- Sarasvathy, S. (2014). The downside of entrepreneurial opportunities. *Management*, 17(4), 305-315.
- Shapero, A., & Sokol, L. (1982). The social dimensions of entrepreneurship. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign's Academy for Entrepreneurial Leadership Historical Research Reference in Entrepreneurship.
- Tomy, S., & Pardede, E. (2020). An entrepreneurial intention model focussing on higher education. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*.
- Thompson, E. R. (2009). Individual entrepreneurial intent : Construct clarification and development of an internationally reliable metric. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 33(3), 669-694.
- Tounés, A. (2006). L'intention entrepreneuriale des étudiants : Le cas français. *La revue des sciences de gestion*, 3, 57-65.
- Varraut, N. (1998). Démarche stratégique du dirigeant-proprétaire de PME. 4ème Congrès International Francophone sur le PME
- Vélez, C. I., Bustamante, M. A., Loor, B. A., & Afcha, S. M. (2020). La educación para el emprendimiento como predictor de una intención emprendedora de estudiantes universitarios. *Formación universitaria*, 13(2), 63-72.